

QUALITMETRY AND ITS MAIN FEATURES IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION

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Abstract: First of all, it is necessary to determine that qualimetry is a science of quality. Accordingly, the central concept to be considered will be the quality expressed in a large array of properties and properties. Again, when we consider each subject in its closed evaluation system for the application of qualimetry, the quality is represented by specific indicators. The meaning of qualimetry is to develop the principles of an assessment system that can be applied universally to all objects of research or individual product groups. The object of qualimetry can mean a conditional product in which a certain characteristic (a system of properties and parameters) and a quality control method are applied.

Key words: Qualimetry, notion, methods, and branches of qualimetry, natural and social indicators.

The concept of the qualimetric aspect is also important, which already reflects the technological side of the application of qualimetry methods, combining systematic concepts of assessment such as structure, property, dynamism, etc. the relationship between the matrix of evaluation parameters and individual indicators with a certain hierarchy.

A more accurate formulation of the goals and objectives of qualimetry also helps to divide it into areas of use. In particular, the following types of modern qualimetry are distinguished: 1-General. It deals with the development of general theoretical problems, including theories of evaluation and measurement, systems of concepts and axiomatics.

2-Special. It is a narrow cross-section qualimetry in terms of coverage and applied assessment methods. For example, in social qualimetry, comprehensive methods can be used, which include expert, index, probability-statistical, etc. as a result of the complex processing of the data obtained, an expert opinion is drawn on the quality of a particular social environment. In addition, evaluation systems themselves can be multifaceted, which leads to the presence of conventions when concluding about the qualitative state of the object under study.

Qualimetry is a science that studies the problems and methodology of assessing the quality of all objects in nature and processes occurring in society, products created

in the field of production. It is a branch of science that combines the methods of evaluating the quality of objects, products, processes, and determines the result achieved using various methods and tools. From the point of view of modern times, quality indicators of qualimetry are divided into two large groups - natural and social indicators. Natural indicators, in turn, are divided into physical, chemical and biological quantitative indicators of the studied object. Social indicators are used in relation to events, production and consumption products, pedagogical processes, the position and place of a person in social and independent life, literacy, level of upbringing, personal maturity at a certain stage of the development of society. Qualimetrics comprehensively studies the quantitative and qualitative indicators of each group mentioned above and develops a general evaluation procedure. The diagnosis and quantitative assessment of the quality of objects and products was established in the 15th century, and at first craftsmen determined the indicators that determine the quality of their products and began to put quality marks. In this way, commodity science was born and in 1549, the first department of "Commodity Science" was established at Paduan University in Italy.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the evaluation and standardization of objects and products by means of points was established in the USA and European countries. In this way, in other countries, certain works have been started to determine the quality indicators and to use them in practice. These actions motivated the emergence of qualimetry as a scientific discipline and the expansion of the scope of research. There are three theoretical (general), special and practical branches of qualimetry. In theoretical qualimetry, a specific object is designed (abstracted) and the general laws and mathematical models of its quality indicators are studied. The research object of theoretical qualimetry is the development of philosophical and methodological bases of quantitative assessment of the quality of objects, production products, objects and subjects. In the practical fields of theoretical qualimetry, the methodology and theoretical foundations of quality assessment of various objects and processes have a common feature. Special qualimetry develops a precise methodology and mathematical model for evaluating the quality of objects used for various purposes.

There are types of special qualimetry, such as expert, probabilistic-statistical, index, qualimetric taxonomy. Applied qualimetry is a field that develops quality assessment of technology, production, human activity, various projects and processes. It is interconnected with other disciplines and has branches such as technical qualimetry, social qualimetry, pedagogical qualimetry, medical

qualimetry, geological qualimetry. Pedagogical qualimetry is a scientific-theoretical science that was created and formed on the basis of experiences and evidence collected over the years. In this case, professional qualifications and pedagogical skills of pedagogues are determined by comparison.

Methodological problems of pedagogical quality metrics have so far been overlooked by scientific researchers and they are waiting for their solution. The research object of pedagogical qualimetry is the quality of the educational process, the organization and management of the educational activities of the students, the control and evaluation of the teacher's activities. The history of the formation and development of pedagogical qualimetry as a science can be conditionally divided into three periods:

1. Early Middle and Middle Ages, that is, the period of empirical development that is not yet scientifically based.
2. The end of the 16th and 19th centuries is the period when the first idea about the quality of the educational process appeared.
3. The period of new and newest development of pedagogical qualimetry, i.e. the period of scientifically based, defined methodological foundations, with theoretical, special and practical branches, scientific measurement parameters.

Pedagogical qualimetry as a science has the following conceptual foundations:

1. Pedagogical qualimetry allows to determine and draw conclusions about the quality of the educational process organized at various stages of continuous education, the level of learning of learners, and the professional qualifications of pedagogical personnel.
2. Takes the quality indicator of the researched object as a dynamic category and assumes that the level of quality will increase in the future, keeping pace with the times, on the basis of social orders placed before continuous education.
3. Pedagogical qualimetry is formed and develops as a science based on the achievements of two interrelated fields - theoretical and practical qualimetry.
4. Pedagogical qualimetry is the compatibility of the level of training of future teachers with the qualification requirements, the professional qualifications of teachers working in the continuous education system, the quality of the educational process organized at this stage, the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications, professional competence (competence) compliance with DTS, higher education institutions, including the quality of training of pedagogical personnel of existing departments, the quality of material and didactic support of the courses included in

the curriculum is controlled based on the rating in accordance with the established procedure and evaluates.

Pedagogical qualimetry as a science determines the way to achieve the following goals:

- 1) Ideological and political changes taking place in the world, achievements achieved in educational institutions of the developed countries of the world, spiritual and educational updates in the life of society. taking into account the development of normative requirements that allow to control the organization of the educational process in accordance with the requirements of the time;
- 2) At the stage of creating legal and regulatory documents of the educational process, DTS based on state and social orders, model curricula based on qualification requirements for pedagogues, modernized and integrated model programs introduced in the continuous education system, development of ways to control the appropriateness of the material and technical, educational and methodological provision of educational courses and evaluate their quality;
- 3) Formation of standards for quality control and evaluation of the educational process, educational and pedagogical practice in higher education institutions;
- 4) Providing employment to graduates of higher educational institutions, adapting them to the pedagogical process, developing standards for analyzing and evaluating the content of work conducted in the mentor-student direction.

The main tasks of pedagogical qualimetry as a science:

- control of the implementation of the tasks specified in the Law "On Education", the National Program of Personnel Training, state programs, presidential decrees, decisions and orders, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers;
- development of normative documents and rating system of the certification and accreditation process of higher education institutions;
- to determine the scientific potential of the departments of higher educational institutions, scientific research, spiritual and educational work, the quality of the organized educational process;
- to determine the quality of pedagogical activity of professors, scientific research, spiritual and educational works, material-technical, educational-methodical complexes of taught courses. Pedagogical qualimetry includes comparison of research methods, analysis of the obtained results with the help of mathematical statistical methods and drawing conclusions, conducting interviews with pedagogical personnel, conducting a survey to determine the opinions of teachers, carrying out an examination, social methods can be entered.

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